

Popular Article

Growth Curve study through body weight of animal

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Abstract

Animal growth models are used to estimate the daily food requirements for animals of various ages and genetic categories as well as to identify alternative techniques to increase the efficiency of livestock production. It has also been used to calculate the increase in live weight and adult body weight. Animal associated with the normal exhibits an S-shaped sigmoidal pattern, and a number of nonlinear functions have been employed to model animal growth as a function of age.

Introduction

One of the fundamental traits in farm animals is growth. An increase in cell volume and number is associated with body growth. Growth in any trait is the outcome of an individual's genetic potential and the genetic x environmental interaction. The time (or age) related changes in yield carried on by such interaction are explained as the growth curve (Sunwasiya *et al.*, 2020; Kor A. *et al.*, 2006). Age-related changes can be seen in the composition of tissues, the size and quantity of cells, the weight of any organ and the live weight (Sunwasiya *et al.*, 2020; Eisen, 1976). Researchers who defined growth using a variety of growth models on different breeds found that the perception of growth differed by breed and model (Mukundan *et al.*, 1982; Jenkins and Leymaster, 1993; Kocabas *et al.*, 1997; Akbas *et al.*, 1999; Sunwasiya *et al.*, 2020). Various researchers reported growth curves in animal to estimate adult body weight and increase in live weight (Bhadula and Bhat, 1980; Mukundan *et al.*, 1982; Moore, 1986; Salah *et al.*, 1988; Nasholm, 1990; Nasholm and Danell, 1992; Jenkins and Leymaster, 1993; Sunwasiya *et al.*, 2020).

Different Non-linear Growth Curve models

1. Brody,
2. Von-Bertalanffy,
3. Verhulst,
4. Logistic
5. Gompertz models,
6. Richards

Importance of Non-linear Growth Curve models

Birth, weaning, yearling weight gain efficiency are growth characteristics that are economically significant in relation to the cost of production. The physical and financial viability of a kid are reflected in its growth. Weaning weight provides a good indication of the kid's performance moving later. Numerous studies demonstrate the influence of hereditary and non-genetic factors on kid's growth traits at various ages in various goat breeds (Rai et al., 2004; Gopal R. Gowane et al., 2011; Tyagi et al., 2013; Singh, P. et al., 2013; Kuthu ZH et al., 2015; Sunwasiya et al., 2020). Animal development features are influenced by a variety of genetic and non-genetic factors, which must be taken into consideration in order to accurately estimate genetic parameters and, ultimately, for evolution of selection strategies.

Conclusion

Because growth curves predict future growth at any age, they can be used to pre-selection of animals. The optimum slaughter age can also be predicted using growth models.

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